

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE UYGUR DUTOR AND ITS PERFORMANCE STYLES

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Abstract: The Uyghurs have a rich cultural heritage, and their language, literature, music, and traditions are a reflection of the long historical development of the people. The culture of the Uyghur people is a harmonious combination of Eastern and Western cultures, a rich heritage that has been formed over the centuries. The dutor is one of the most important instruments in Uyghur musical culture. This article provides information about the performance styles and unique characteristics of the Uyghur national dutor.

Keywords: Culture, heritage, genre, instrument, muqam, solo, ensemble, resonator, source, melody.

Introduction.

The Uyghurs are one of the ancient peoples of Central Asia, living mainly in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region of the People's Republic of China. In addition, there is a Uyghur diaspora in Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkey and other countries. The Uyghurs have a rich cultural heritage, and their language, literature, music and traditions are an expression of the long historical development of the people. The culture of the Uyghur people is a harmonious form of Eastern and Western cultures, a rich heritage that has been formed over the centuries. Their language, art, music and traditions have retained their charm even today. Preserving and studying this culture, as well as passing on the historical heritage to future generations, are important tasks. Uyghur folk music has a rich and diverse genre, reflecting the cultural heritage of the people. The following genres are mainly widespread:

1. Muqam - one of the most basic and complex genres of Uyghur music, which includes classical traditional melodies. It is performed to the accompaniment of various musical instruments and has long, complex rhythms.

2. Folk songs - simple and pleasant melodies that mainly describe love, nature, work and social life.

3. Dance melodies and rhythms - special melodies for popular dances of the Uyghur people, which are fast and rhythmic in nature.

4. Religious and ceremonial music - songs and musical works related to the Islamic religion and traditional Uyghur ceremonies.

The dutor plays an important role in the Uyghur musical tradition and is actively used in the above genres. The dutor occupies an important place in Uyghur musical culture and is used as one of the main instruments in many folk songs. Uyghur folk music is rich in various genres, and the dutor is performed both as a solo instrument and as part of an ensemble. In particular, the dutor plays a large role in the Uyghur traditional music genre called "Muqom", where it is the main instrument of traditional melodies. Dutor melodies often express human emotions, love, and images of nature. Its performance is also combined with traditional

Uyghur dances, which demonstrates the unity of national music and art. The Uyghur people have a rich cultural heritage, one of the components of which is the dutor. The dutor is a stringed instrument widely used among many peoples of Central Asia and occupies a special place in Uyghur musical culture. In this article, we will talk about the origin, development, and importance of the Uyghur dutor in music. The dutor is one of the most ancient musical instruments, the history of its appearance dates back several thousand years. According to historical sources, the dutar first appeared in Central Asia and China. Archaeological finds show that the ancient Uyghurs widely used stringed instruments and that their musical traditions have been formed over the centuries.

The Uyghur dutor is distinguished by its unique shape and structure. It is mainly two-stringed, and some variants can also have three or four strings. The dutor is made of wood, and its body is specially shaped to produce a resonant sound as a resonant string instrument. The sound of the Uyghur dutor is delicate and melodious, and the melodies played with it have a lyrical and dramatic spirit that reaches the heart. Structure of the Uyghur Dutor The Uyghur dutor is made of wood, usually carved from the trunk of a mulberry or walnut tree. It consists of the following main parts:

1. The body (corpus) is a resonance box that amplifies the sound and gives it resonance. It is usually round or slightly oblong in shape.
2. The hollow part (resonator) - the quality of the dutor's sound depends on the processing of this part, and is closed with a thin wooden plate.
3. Neck (stalk) - long and thin, on which the frets (notes) are located. The frets can be made of silk or special silk fibers.
4. Strings - mainly two, sometimes three or four-stringed variants are also found. The strings are made of silk or metal wires.
5. Chimildiq and burgul - parts used to tune the strings, through which the tension of the strings is adjusted.

The Uyghur dutor is an integral part of the "Twelve Muqam" system and plays an important role in the performance of muqams. It is one of the main instruments in the rich musical heritage of the Uyghur people and serves as the leading instrument in the performance of traditional muqams. In the traditional musical system of the Uyghur people "Twelve Muqams", the dutor is recognized as one of the main instruments. Muqams are usually long and consist of several parts. The dutor plays a leading role in the performance of these muqams, especially in the following aspects: The opening part of the muqam - the dutor - sets the main melody at the beginning of the muqam. The middle and fast parts - serve as a rhythmic driving force. Solo and ensemble performance - the dutor can be performed both alone and with other instruments.

The dutor plays an important role in Uyghur musical culture and is used as one of the main instruments in many folk songs. Uyghur folk music is rich in various genres, and the dutor is performed both as a solo instrument and as part of an ensemble. In particular, the dutor plays a large role in the Uyghur traditional music genre called "Muqam", where it is the main instrument of traditional songs.

Conclusion

The Uyghur dutor has developed over the centuries and has become an integral part of Uyghur culture and music. It is not only a national heritage, but also one of the most important musical instruments in the history of world music. Today, the dutor is lovingly performed by

Uyghur musicians, and through its unique sound, national traditions are passed down from generation to generation.

List of used literature:

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